

ISLAMIS A RELIGION OF KNOWLEDGE

Omonov Fazliddin Asadulla o'g'li

Termiz State University, Faculty of History, 3rd year.

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Abstract: Islam is a religion of knowledge. According to Islam, acquiring knowledge is one of the obligatory actions for every Muslim man and woman. The fact that the word knowledge is repeated 765 times in our holy book "Qur'an Karim" proves our above words. In the history of the Uzbek people, there have been two renaissances, and for both of our renaissances, Islam plays a very important role.

We know that the Arabs brought Islam to our country in the 8th century. The Arab people were not as highly cultured as we are. But there was a special culture in Islam. As Islam spread to the minds of our people, they realized how necessary knowledge is. In previous religious views, worldly knowledge was condemned, and people who studied it were punished. In the religion of Islam, one is called to study both religious and secular knowledge. In the 11th verse of Surah Mujadala of our holy book, the Holy Qur'an, it is said: "Allah will raise those among you who believe and are endowed with knowledge."

One of the important features of Islam is that it provides an opportunity for representatives of the peoples who have accepted it to participate in the development of Islamic beliefs. It goes through 3 distinct developmental stages or periods. The first can be tentatively called the Qur'anic period. The religio-political and social views, legal and moral criteria, reflecting the level of religious consciousness of the people of Arabia reflected in the Holy Qur'an, are undoubtedly common values for the entire Muslim world. The second period, which lasted for almost 4 centuries, is distinguished by the fact that different opinions were allowed in Islam under the rule of all-Islamic rulings. The directions, sects and factions in Islam appeared during this period. The religious unity of Muslims has become an intractable problem. In the 10th and 11th centuries, the relations between the traditional Sunnis and the Imami Shiites, Mu'tazilites and Ash'arites became particularly tense. Caliph Qadir (991 - 1031) tried to establish traditional Islam as the state religion, obligatory for all under the law. For this purpose, the "Powerful Symbol of Religion" signed by theologians loyal to the tradition was announced. In it, the main rules of the traditional religious doctrine, which was declared as the "true religion", were described in detail, and deviation from it was considered as disbelief worthy of punishment. However, this event did not lead to the establishment of religious

unity in Islam. The ideological struggle continued in the following centuries. The third stage of development in Islam is connected with the increasing importance and place of the "periphery" countries of the Muslim world. When nations with completely different cultural traditions joined the spiritual life of the Muslim world, they brought their religious and moral ideas, legal norms and customs to Islam. In such large historical and cultural regions as Movarounnahr, Iran, North Africa, India, Indonesia, Islam acquires its own characteristics.

A person who takes Islam to his heart realizes how important knowledge is for a person. Our great scholars, such as Imam al-Bukhari, Ibn Sina, Al-Biruni, Isa Termizi, Az-Zamakhshari, Imam Moturidi, Alisher Navai, Amir Temur, memorized the Holy Qur'an. In particular, Imam Bukhari and Al-Hakim At-Tirmizi, who were his students, were unparalleled in the science of hadith. Az Zamakhshari's treatise on Qur'an interpretation is still used in institutions in Egypt. Ibn Sina's work "Medical Laws", dedicated to the science of medicine, was used as the main manual in Europe until the 17th century. Our great grandfather Amir Temur became the spreader of Islam, or Fatih. We can list many of these names. But today our nation is lagging behind in science. Why are great scholars not emerging in the age of technical progress? The reason is that we have not deeply understood our religion and taken it to heart. Our great Companions, famous scientists and thinkers have also given many hadiths and narrations about how important science is to human spirituality. In the hadith shared by Abu Huraira (r.a.), our Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said, "Whoever goes on the path of seeking knowledge, Allah will make the path to Paradise easier for him." There can be no more propaganda than this to encourage science.

The fact that one of the ways to heaven, which is the highest goal of every human being, is through science, should invite each of us to science. As we said above, Islam is a religion of knowledge. A person who has absorbed Islam in his heart understands knowledge. Respected President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said "Islam means understanding the truth. He encourages people to do good deeds. His words, "He calls each of us to goodness and peace, teaches us to be a real person," also confirm our above words.

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